

Delay-Reduction in Edge Computing Environment throughout a Heuristic Algorithm

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1 Introduction

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Information Technology

1 Introduction

- **Information Technology (IT):**
 - has developed dramatically with about 50-billion IoT devices.
- **Internet of Things (IoT):**
 - production of complex and computation-intensive IoT applications that generate a big data.
 - medical, industrial, agriculture, enterprise, energy, and infrastructure.
 - an example, IoT healthcare wearables: smart watches (real-time healthcare data).
- **Limitations:**
 - limitations in power and computational capabilities (i.e., CPU and memory) on the execution of such resource-demanding applications on the devices.

Cloud & Edge Computing

1 Introduction

- **Cloud Computing:**
 - can support this growth by allowing on-demand access to a massive pool of computation resources.
- **Cloud Computing Problems:**
 - centralized and far distance, security problems, generating a high delay and latency, interrupting the seamless of real-time interaction and violation of QoS.
- **An example:**
 - some applications are critical to time such as healthcare application (medical IoT application). cloud not be useful.
- **Edge Computing (new paradigm):**
 - secure platform, reduce delay and latency, enable interaction for real-time applications, and enhance the quality of services by providing a pool of computational and storage capabilities at the edge and fog level of networks where they are close to IoT devices.

Cloud & Edge Computing cont.

1 Introduction

Edge Computing

Figure: 1 Cloud and Edge Computing [1].

Edge User Allocation (EUA)

1 Introduction

- **Edge server limitations [2]:**
 - limited resources which might not be able to serve all users within its coverage, some of users might also be allocated in other coverage of the edge servers, or be allocated to cloud.
- **Edge User Allocation (EUA):**
 - to ensure the QoS, the optimization target is to maximize the number of users allotted to edge servers and reduce the number of edge servers required to serve those users [3, 4].
 - EUA is the term used to describe the issue of allocating efficiently user tasks to edge servers.
 - The EUA problem is NP-hardness which becomes hard to solve effectively in an expanding edge computing environment.
- In this work, we propose a heuristic approach to solve the EUA problem and reduce the delay of application execution on the edge network.

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2 Our Contribution

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A New Heuristic for the EUA Problem

2 Our Contribution

- Proposing a heuristic to solve NP-hardness of the EUA problem.
- Solving the complexity of the EUA problem by finding the optimal solution for user tasks.
- Reduces the delay of execution time-aware applications such as real time applications.
- Maximizing the number of allocated users.
- Minimizing the required edge servers.
- Using a real-world dataset (EUA) [5], extensive evaluations are performed to demonstrate the efficiency of the new approach.
- Our approach outperforms some of the baseline and state-of-the-art approaches.

A Heuristic Flow Chart

2 Our Contribution

Figure: 2 The Flow Chart of the Heuristic Algorithm.

A Heuristic Pseudocode

2 Our Contribution

Pseudocode

1. **Initialization**
2. a set of edge servers S and a set of users U
3. all users u_j , $\forall u_j \in U$, are unallocated
4. **end initialization**
5. Sort edge server S in descending order according to their capacity of CPU, RAM, Storage, and Bandwidth, i.e. [20: highest, 1: lowest]
6. Sort user u in ascending order of their priority, i.e. [1: highest, 10: lowest]
7. Calculate the distance between user u with highest priority and edge server s with highest capacity to find the nearest edge server s to user u
8. **for each user $u_j \in U$ do**
9. $S_{u_j} \triangleq$ user u_j 's nearest edge servers;
10. $S_{u_j}^{active} \triangleq$ user u_j 's active nearest edge servers;
11. **if $S_{u_j}^{active} \neq \emptyset$ then**
12. **allocate user u_j to a nearest edge server $s_i \in S_{u_j}^{active}$ which has the highest capacity**
13. **else**

A Heuristic Pseudocode cont.

2 Our Contribution

Pseudocode

14. allocate user u_j to a nearest edge server $s_i \in S_{u_j}$ which has the highest capacity
15. end if
16. if s_i cannot be decided then
17. allocate user u_j to the central cloud server
18. end if
19. end for

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3 Results

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Results (Experimental Settings)

3 Results

Table: Experimental Settings [1]

	Users	Edge servers	Available resources (μ)
Set #1	100, ..., 1000	50%	35
Set #2	500	10%, ..., 100%	35
Set #3	500	50%	30, 35, ..., 75

Results (Users)

3 Results

Figure: 3 Elapsed CPU time vs. Number of users (Set #1).

Results (Servers)

3 Results

Figure: 4 Elapsed CPU time vs. Number of edge servers (Set #2).

Results (Capacity)

3 Results

Figure: 5 Elapsed CPU time vs. Edge server capacity (Set #3).

Results (Users)

3 Results

Figure: 6 Elapsed CPU time vs. Number of users (Set #1) without Optimal and ICSOC19.

Results (Servers)

3 Results

Figure: 7 Elapsed CPU time vs. Number of edge servers (Set #2) without Optimal and ICSOC19.

Results (Capacity)

3 Results

Figure: 8 Elapsed CPU time vs. Edge server capacity (Set #3) without Optimal and ICSOC19.

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4 Conclusion

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Summery & Conclusion

4 Conclusion

- Cloud Computing.
- Edge Computing.
- Edge User Allocation.
- New heuristic approach.
- Outperforms the baseline approach (Optimal) and state-of-the-art approaches (ICSOC19 and TPDS20).
- In the future, extend to support user mobility and utilizing Fog Computing.

References

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- [3] Jennings, Brendan, and Rolf Stadler. "Resource management in clouds: Survey and research challenges." *Journal of Network and Systems Management* 23 (2015): 567-619.
- [4] <https://github.com/swinedge/eua-dataset>.

Thank you for listening!
Your feedback will be highly appreciated!

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